

Organisation [University of Évora]
Department [Renewable Energies Chair]

Deliverable 1.6

Gender Equality Report

Sol2H2O

Date: **25.08.2025**

Doc. Version: **1**

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Gender Equality Report
Project Title:	Sol2H2O
Document Author:	Dominique Livreiro
Project Owner:	European Commission
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta (UEVORA)
Doc. Version:	1
Sensitivity:	Public
Date:	25.08.2025

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Pedro Horta (UEVORA)	PM	<i>Accepted Conditionally</i>	30.09.2025
Guillermo Zaragoza (CIEMAT)	PSC	<i>Accepted Conditionally</i>	30.09.2025
Juan Antonio Bencomo (ITC)	PSC	<i>Accepted Conditionally</i>	30.09.2025
Andrea Cipollina (UNIPA)	PSC	<i>Accepted Conditionally</i>	30.09.2025

Document history:

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarised in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in *project folder*.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	3
2. Sol2H2O Gender Balance	4
2.1 Consortium Institutions	4
2.1.1 UÉvora	4
2.1.2 CIEMAT	5
2.1.3 ITC	5
2.1.4 UNIPA	5
2.1.5 Comparison	5
2.2 Sol2H2O teams	6
2.2.1 M17 teams	7
2.2.2 M34 teams	7
2.2.3 Gender balance in Sol2H2O top positions	8
2.2.4 Gender balance in Sol2H2O activities	8
2.3 Sol2H2O events	10
2.3.1 Fast-Track Schools	10
2.3.2 Other events	11
3. GEP Comparison	14
4. GE actions in the Consortium and GE events attended by the Sol2H2O team	16
4.1 GE Actions in the Consortium	16
4.2 GE Events attended	18
5. Sol2H2O GE Seminars	19
5.1 ProM#2 GE Seminar	20
5.2 ProM#3 GE Seminar	21
5.3 ProM#4 GE Seminar	22
5.4 ProM#7 GE Seminar	23
6. Surveys	24
6.1 Sol2H2O teams GE Survey	24
6.2 FTSS GE Survey	27
7. GE in the Sol2H2O Communication channels	29
7.1 Meet our team	30
7.2 Website	31
7.3 Newsletters	32
7.4 Social networks	33
7.5 Project video	35
8. Gender Equality action barriers	36
9. Measures to propose to the institutional administrations	36
10. Conclusions	37
10.1 Work-Life Balance and Organisational Culture	38
10.2 Gender Balance in Leadership and Decision-making	38
10.3 Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression	39
10.4 Integration of the Gender Dimension into Research and Teaching Content	39
10.5 Measures against Gender-based Violence, including Sexual harassment	39
10.6 Other relevant topics	39
11. Related Plans (following PM2 methodology)	40
Appendix 1: References and Related Documents	41
Appendix 2: GE Seminars presentations	43
Appendix 3: Sol2H2O team GE Survey	72
Appendix 4: FTSS GE Survey	83

1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of Sol2H2O¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D1.6 - Gender Equality Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

D1.6 is a report on the implementation and impacts of the Gender Equality (GE) activities in Sol2H2O, pertaining to Task 1.4, which aimed at the development and implementation of questionnaires, 4 dedicated seminars, monitoring procedures and enhancement strategies for Gender Equality in the access to research and technical-administrative positions in the Consortium institutions, concurring with the attractiveness of Young Researchers to UÉvora (Sol2H2O Objective 3).

Led by UÉvora, Task 1.4 acknowledges the importance of promoting and monitoring Gender Equality aspects both in the Widening upgrade and in having a gender balanced perspective in research and technical-administrative teams. The activities are based on the UÉvora Gender Equality Plan - GEP (first version in 2022-2023, second version for 2024-2026, including an English translation), which focuses on the following aspects, according to the Horizon Europe recommendations:

- work-life balance and organisational culture;
- gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content;
- measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

Horizon Europe prioritises gender equality, aiming to integrate it into research and innovation content and ensure gender-equal working environments, aiming to eliminate gender and intersecting inequalities.

Several statistics show that there is still work to be done to achieve this goal, for instance, women accounted for 24% of employees in the EU energy sector in 2022, and in renewable energy, women represented 32% of full-time employees globally in 2018².

At the EU level, considering all fields, gender balance is achieved among university students and graduates, but as women advance in academia, their representation decreases, especially at top positions, holding only 30% of full professorship (or equivalent) positions. In Science and Engineering, this percentage drops to 20%. Women remain underrepresented as authors in the field of Engineering and Technology, and women comprised only 9% of patent applicants in the 2018-2021 period³.

However, gender diversity is not only fair but also represents an advantage for research and innovation. First, for not leaving a huge potential of talent unexplored. Then, because several studies found that a high proportion of women in scientific teams contributes to successful team collaboration (possibly, because women show greater social sensitivity, being more likely to collaborate and being more democratic), catalysing creativity and innovation, increasing collective intelligence and best outcomes. Nevertheless, there isn't an ideal proportion of women on a team established, also because it is not only a question of *"the number of women, but rather how women on teams are integrated and empowered"*⁴.

¹ Project: 101079305 — Sol2H2O — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

² Webinar "Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition", European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), in the 14th of November of 2023

³ "She Figures 2024 - Research and Innovation", <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/she-figures-2024>

⁴ Love, H.B., Stephens, A., Fosdick, B.K., *et al.* The impact of gender diversity on scientific research teams: a need to broaden and accelerate future research. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 9, 386 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01389-w>

To monitor the gender balance, a comparison of the 4 partners' GEPs (UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA) was held, as well as an analysis of the number of employees by gender.

The UÉvora team attended dedicated GE events and organised an internal leadership training.

Three dedicated seminars have already been held, alongside project meetings, and a fourth one is foreseen for the final meeting in November 2025. These seminars addressed different topics and promoted debates.

A survey was conducted using a questionnaire applied to all the consortium Sol2H2O teams and to the Fast-Track Schools (FTS) participants.

This topic was also covered in the project's communication channels, and the mentioned activities are detailed below.

2. Sol2H2O GENDER BALANCE

Gender analysis provides information on the different roles of women and men at different levels in institutions and projects, enabling an understanding of gender inequalities. When focused on institutions, gender analysis is also important in determining how institutions themselves are also 'gendered', for example, in the workplace in terms of recruitment practices, the gendered divisions of labour and women's access to decision-making positions⁵.

Therefore, the data provided by UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA were compared, taking into account the employees of these institutions in general, and the Sol2H2O team members, in specific (both by M17 and M34). The gender proportion of the FTS participants was also analysed.

2.1 Consortium Institutions

2.1.1 UÉvora

Throughout 2021, in UÉvora, a gender diagnosis was held entitled "Perceções e Realidades sobre a (In)Visibilidade de Género na Universidade de Évora. Relatório de diagnóstico institucional"⁶ (Perceptions and Realities on Gender (In)Visibility at the University of Évora. Institutional diagnostic report). The document was published in January 2022. Contributions were collected from employees at all hierarchical levels and functional areas, ensuring a plural and representative view. In the same year, the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) was published, based on the results of the diagnosis.

In this diagnosis, it was verified that from the 1121 employees (in 2021), 54.77% were women and 45.23% were men. In the professors and researchers category, 47.17% were women and 52.84% men, and in the non-teaching staff (including scholarship holders), 62% were women and 38% were men.

Regarding the top positions, the percentages were: leading researchers - 33.3% women, 66.7% men; full professors - 33.3% women, 66.7% men; non-teaching managers - 64.9% women, 35.1% men.

By 2022, the Renewable Energies Chair - CER (where the Sol2H2O team is included), from UÉvora, presented the most significant male overrepresentation, with 80.55% of men and 19.45% of women among the researchers and scholarship holders. Nowadays (January 2025), this percentage has changed, along with the growth of the group to 72% of men and 28% of women.

⁵ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/tools-methods/gender-analysis>

⁶ <https://uevora.pt/rdpc/handle/10174/33273>

A new diagnostic report in UÉvora is foreseen for 2026.

2.1.2 CIEMAT

In CIEMAT, in 2020, there were around a thousand employees, of whom 58.41% were men and 41.59% women. Between scholarship and training staff, there was a better balance, 50.60% of men and 49.4% of women. However, the presence of women in senior positions was lower, less than 40%.

2.1.3 ITC

In ITC, a diagnosis was held in 2019, and of the 187 employees, 96 were women (51.3%), and 91 were men (48.7%). Table 2.1.3.1 presents these percentages by position category.

Table 2.1.3.1: Percentage of women and men, by category, in ITC (2019)

Position Category	Men (%)	Women (%)
Researchers and managers (top positions)	56.07	43.93
Administrative, technicians and other staff	38.75	61.25
Overall	48.70	51.30

In 2023, a new gender balance was held: from a total of 243 employees, 117 were women (48.15%), and 126 were men (51.85%). Table 2.1.3.2 presents these percentages by position category.

Table 2.1.3.2: Percentage of women and men, by category, in ITC (2023)

Position Category	Men (%)	Women (%)
Researchers and managers (top positions)	53.39	46.61
Administrative, technicians and other staff	50.40	49.60
Overall	51.85	48.15

2.1.4 UNIPA

In UNIPA, in 2020, there were 61.5% of men and 38.5% of women among professors and researchers, noting that, as the position becomes more elevated, the presence of women tends to decrease.

2.1.5 Comparison

For all four institutions, it was possible to access data, though from different years (2019 to 2023), and not for all categories. More recent data were not assessed.

It was verified that, at UÉvora, the Human Resources database does not include gender data for all employees, which makes it difficult to check the number of women and men in the institution regularly. This is one of the measures that the Widening partner could develop.

To enable the comparison between the partners' institutions, in Table 2.1.5.1 and Figure 2.1.5.1, employees are presented by gender (women and men) and by general category, if assessed: "researchers" (including researchers, professors, and leadership positions) and

“other staff” (including scholarship holders, administrative staff and technicians). Noting that the data refer to the closest years among those accessed.

Table 2.1.5.1: Percentage of women and men, by category, in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA

Partner	Researchers - Men (%)	Researchers - Women (%)	Other staff - Men (%)	Other staff - Women (%)	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora (2021)	52.84	47.17	38.02	61.98	45.23	54.77
CIEMAT (2020)	-	-	-	-	58.41	41.59
ITC (2019)	56.07	43.93	38.75	61.25	48.70	51.30
UNIPA (2020)	61.50	38.50	-	-	-	-

Figure 2.1.5.1: Proportion of women and men, in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA (*only researchers and professors)

2.2 Sol2H2O teams

The number of women and men in the four Sol2H2O partners’ teams was monitored both when submitting D1.4 - Progress Report, in M17 (April 2024), and in M34 (September 2025) for this D1.6, to make an assessment of the gender balance in the project and its evolution, as new members joined the team. Overall, there was an increase in the gender balance, as the new members in the teams were male researchers, although the women are divided between researchers and “other staff”.

The WP leaders' positions in the four partners teams are occupied by men.

Fewer women and for less time went on mobility. A significantly lower number of CYR (PhD students) are women, on the other hand, the number of YR, for the all project, presents a higher number of women researchers. The mentoring program showed a significant gender unbalance, with more men registering, though there was a low number of registrations.

Figure 2.2.1: Sol2H2O team in ProM#2 meeting (July 23) and in ProM#6 (June 25)

2.2.1 M17 teams

In M17 (April 2024), the Sol2H2O teams (researchers and other workforce involved in the project's Action) were distributed by gender as follows in Table 2.2.1.1 and Figure 2.2.2.1.

Table 2.2.1.1: Gender distribution in the Sol2H2O team in M17

Partner	Researchers - Men	Researchers - Women	Other staff - Men	Other staff - Women	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora	2	1	0	4	28.6	71.4
CIEMAT	2	6	0	1	22.2	77.8
ITC	3	0	0	1	75	25
UNIPA	3	1	0	2	50	50
Total	10	8	0	8	38.46	61.54

2.2.2 M34 teams

In M34 (September 2025), the Sol2H2O teams (researchers and other workforce involved in the project's Action) were distributed by gender as follows in Table 2.2.2.1 and Figure 2.2.2.1.

Table 2.2.2.1: Gender distribution in the Sol2H2O team in M34

Partner	Researchers - Men	Researchers - Women	Other staff - Men	Other staff - Women	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora	4	1	0	4	44.44	55.56
CIEMAT	3	5	0	1	33.33	66.67
ITC	4	0	0	1	80	20
UNIPA	6	2	1	2	63.64	36.36
Total	17	8	1	8	52.94	47.06

Figure 2.2.2.1: Proportion of women and men, by category, in Sol2H2O, in M17 and in M34

2.2.3 Gender balance in Sol2H2O top positions

The PSC - Project Steering Committee, including all the WP leaders (one per partner), is composed of 4 men.

2.2.4 Gender balance in Sol2H2O activities

The Sol2H2O teams took part in activities in the scope of the project (see D3.3 Career attractiveness framework report), including a leadership training (only the UÉvora team), mobilities (travels in the scope of project coordination, tutoring and mentoring tasks), PhD thesis tutoring (CYR - Task 3.2), mentoring of YR (Task 3.3), and a mentoring program (in the scope of the Living Amenities Facility, task 3.4), in which the gender balance is presented in this section.

In the leadership training, besides being in itself a GE action (see section 4.1), the gender of the participants can also be assessed: a female coach led the training in May 2025, for 11 participants: 4 women and 7 men, from the UÉvora CER group. A percentage of 36.36% of women participants in the leadership training (1 more woman researcher wanted to participate, but couldn't due to a health problem, which would change the percentage to 41.67%), compared to 28% of women researchers in the CER group, shows that the women in the group want to progress in their careers and feel supported by the team.

Researchers and other staff mobility were held, with the team members of UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA travelling between the partners' institutions' locations to take part in Coordination activities (project meetings, GE seminars, Spin-off seminars, visits to research infrastructures, FTs, tutoring and mentoring tasks, etc.). Table 2.2.4.1 summarises the number of mobilities by partner and by gender, including mobilities to UÉvora already

booked for M36, namely for the final meeting and from TOP partners researchers to the Widening partner.

Table 2.2.4.1: Gender distribution in the Sol2H2O mobilities, researchers and other staff, by M3

Partner	Men (% of mobilities in number of days)	Women (% of mobilities in number of days)	Men (% of persons travelling)	Women (% of persons travelling)
UÉvora	65.45	34.55	44.44	55.56
CIEMAT	34.15	65.83	28.57	71.43
ITC	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
UNIPA	83.87	16.13	70.00	30.00
Total	68.46	31.54	58.06	41.94

Figure 2.2.4.1: UÉvora and ITC researchers (CYR) in a mobility to UNIPA, and ITC researcher in a mobility to UÉvora

With regard to the PhD tutoring activities (Task 3.2, WP3), the Candidate Young Researchers (CYR), by partner and by gender, are presented in Table 2.2.4.2.

Table 2.2.4.2: Gender distribution in the Sol2H2O CYR

Partner	Men (% of CYR)	Women (% of CYR)
UÉvora	100.00	0.00
CIEMAT	0.00	100.00
ITC	-	-
UNIPA	100.00	0.00
Total	66.67	33.33

Regarding the mentoring of Young Researchers (YR) activities (Task 3.3, WP3), the YR, by partner and by gender, are presented in Table 2.2.4.3.

Table 2.2.4.3: Gender distribution in the Sol2H2O YR

Partner	Men (% of YR)	Women (% of YR)
UÉvora	0.00	100.00
CIEMAT	0.00	100.00
ITC	100.00	0.00
UNIPA	50.00	50.00
Total	33.33	66.67

The mentoring program in the scope of the Living Amenities Facility (Task 3.4, WP3), with nine registrations, includes 3 male mentorees, and 6 mentors, 3 women and 3 men, thus a total of 66.67% of men and 33.33% of women.

2.3 Sol2H2O events

2.3.1 Fast-Track Schools

There were three editions of the Sol2H2O FTs (see D3.1), and the gender was collected in all editions.

For FTS#1, there were 46 registrations, with 16 women (34.78%) and 30 men (62.22%). From the registered participants, 42 attended (onsite or online), being 12 women (28.57%) and 30 men (71.43%).

For FTS#2, there were 49 registrations, with 21 women (42.86%) and 28 men (57.14%). From the registered participants, 42 attended (onsite - Figure 2.3.1.1 or online), being 21 women (50%) and 20 men (47.62%), as one of the online attendees was not identified (2.38%).

Figure 2.3.1.1: FTS#2 onsite participants

For FTS#3, there were 43 registrations and 42 answers regarding gender, with 21 women (50%) and 21 men (50%) (Figure 2.3.1.3). From the registered participants, 34 attended (onsite - Figure 2.3.1.4 or online), being 14 women (41.18%) and 19 men (55.88%), as one of the online attendees was not identified (2.94%).

Gender
42 respostas

Figure 2.3.1.3: Gender of the registered participants of FTS#3

Figure 2.3.1.4: FTS#3 onsite participants

2.3.2 Other events

Sol2H2O also organised Fora and Simposia (see D4.1), but the gender was not collected in the registrations, in some cases because the registration was by email, not using a form, in other cases, like in small group debates, the participants were directly invited.

As gender identity refers to “socially constructed attributes, roles, activities, responsibilities and needs”⁷, one's own gender is to be identified by each person, so it can not be deduced by others. With this concept defined, the following statements are limited to observation and contact with participants, as their gender was not questioned to them.

In the Sol2H2O Water-Energy Strategy Symposium (WESSymp), a national symposium organised in Évora, the gender balance appears to be even (Figure 2.3.2.1), and when looking at the participants who took part in a round-table, there were more women representing institutions (Figure 2.3.2.2).

7

https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/gender_en

Figure 2.3.2.1: WESSymp participants

Figure 2.3.2.2: ESSymp round-table participants

In the Sol2H2O Water-Energy Transition Symposium (WETSymp), an international symposium organised online, in the first phase, there was a debate with a small group in each partner country: in the Portuguese day, the participants appeared to be balanced by gender (Figure 2.3.2.3), in the Italian day, the participants were all men, and in the Spanish day, about three quarters of the participants were men.

Figure 2.3.2.3: WETSymp national day: Portugal

In the WETSymp second phase, an international online day was held, and the gender appeared to be unbalanced, with about two-thirds of the participants being males (Figure 2.3.2.4). Following this event, a satisfaction survey was sent to the participants, and of the 34 external participants, 13 answered it, including a question about their gender (Figure 2.3.2.5). Although this sample may not reflect the gender of all the participants, it was answered by 10 men (76.90%) and 3 women (23.10%).

Figure 2.3.2.4: WETSymp international day

5. Gender:
13 respuestas

Figure 2.3.2.5: Gender of the participants answering the WETSymp international day survey

3. GEP COMPARISON

The four partner institutions of the Sol2H2O consortium have published Gender Equality Plans (GEPs, Figure 3.1) and their analysis, together with that of complementary documents⁸, has provided insight into the approaches of UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA to GE issues and institutional diagnostics.

⁸

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/16HaowpPAjGDku2wBkcP5UNJ52uEFpdGe?usp=drive_link

Figure 3.1: UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNiPa’s Gender Equality Plans

The first UÉvora GEP was published in January 2022, with the 2022-2023 strategy, and a similar second version for 2024-2026 was published, including an English translation.

After analysing the four GEPs, it can be concluded that all the Plans follow the European and national legislations, as well as the Horizon Europe guidance on GEPs, focusing on the points:

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

All the institutions have made a situation diagnosis to learn about the gender balance of their employees, with different frequencies, and UÉvora also applied a questionnaire and conducted focus groups to understand the existing perceptions around the previous 5 points. All plans set objectives to be achieved and tools/measures to implement, and agree that continuous monitoring is necessary.

The differences found in the GEPs are mostly in the measures proposed and/or implemented by each institution, as presented in Tables 3.1.1 to 3.1.5.

Table 3.1.1: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNiPa GEPs, point 1

Partner	Work-life balance and organisational culture
All	Flexibility of schedules Use of non-sexist language Teleworking Awareness campaigns and training activities Childcare services
UÉvora	Drafting of a practical guide in inclusive language Summer schools Meetings with a maximum of 2 hours Right to disconnect Time management workshops Takeaway meals service Psychological consultation
CIEMAT	Shifts Satisfaction questionnaire Breastfeeding room (only in the headquarters) Social action plan for costs with dependents
ITC	Right to disconnect

	Adequacy of workspace for pregnant women Inclusive language guides
UNIPA	Summer schools Longer parental leave/Sabbatical semester Psychological consultation

Table 3.1.2: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA GEPs, point 2

Partner	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
All	Monitoring the composition of the leadership bodies Training with experts and mentoring

Table 3.1.3: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA GEPs, point 3

Partner	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
All	Equality in selection boards
UÉvora	Celebration of International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th February) Award for outstanding research in the field of gender studies A minimum of 1/3 of people of each gender in teams applying for project funding
CIEMAT	Celebration of International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th February) Highlighting women in Science Days
ITC	Positive discrimination in hiring (preference to persons of the underrepresented gender)

Table 3.1.4: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA GEPs, point 4

Partner	Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content
All	Training and raising awareness
UÉvora	Include this theme in all the study programmes
UNIPA	Include this theme in all the Master's or doctoral degree programmes Awards and economic incentives for female students in STEM

Table 3.1.5: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA GEPs, point 5

Partner	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment
All	Training In case of complaints: how, to whom, how to manage, conduct code
UÉvora	Scientific and artistic events
UNIPA	Quick guidebook, video, and webpage Regular questionnaires

Overall, the four GEPs identify that in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA, there is a predominantly non-sexist culture, nevertheless, certain positions or functions are occupied by men, and inclusive language must be used.

The UÉvora diagnosis, using focus groups and questionnaires, verified that women are more interested in debating/approaching GE themes, and that there are numerous questions and doubts about how, to whom or whether it is worth reporting gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

4. GE ACTIONS IN THE CONSORTIUM AND GE EVENTS ATTENDED BY THE SOL2H2O TEAM

To promote GE among Sol2H2O partners, relevant documents, campaigns, training courses and other events in which the teams could participate were identified, with particular emphasis on the Widening partner, which could learn from examples applied by TOP partners (see 4.1).

To increase their knowledge and bring more content to the Sol2H2O GE seminars, the technical-administrative members of the UÉvora team participate in events related to GE (see 4.2) and maintain a close collaboration with the University of Évora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion (Gabinete de Igualdade de Género e Inclusão da Universidade de Évora). This Office was established in 2019, but currently has only one employee assigned to it, who often collaborates in the Sol2H2O GE seminars.

4.1 GE Actions in the Consortium

Following a Sol2H2O GE seminar where gender-sensitive communication was referred to, ITC shared their guides: "Comunicar en igualdad - Guía de buenas prácticas y para periodistas y profesionales de la comunicación" and "Incluidapps - Guía 2, normas básicas para el uso del lenguaje inclusivo"⁹.

In 2024, to celebrate the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, CIEMAT Sol2H2O female team members gave some talks in high schools (Figure 4.1.1). In 2025, a female researcher, also from the project, was an invited speaker in the "Women leading Science Event" at the Oslo University (Figure 4.1.2).

Día Internacional de la Mujer y la Niña en la Ciencia

Tratamientos Solares de Agua (TSA)

Plataforma Solar de Almería-CIEMAT

14 febrero 2024

Itzia Berruti Alba Hernández Zandellty
Isabel Esquivela Pavón Paula Serrano Tari

Figure 4.1.1: Alba Ruiz and Paula Serrano (CIEMAT Sol2H2O team) in high school talks (14th February 2024)

⁹ Available in https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/15JG4xjcyHIXdxsZ5ljwxcB2f0yPsnq7?usp=drive_link and <https://www.itccanarias.org/web/es/home/igualdad>

Figure 4.1.2: Isabel Oller (CIEMAT Sol2H2O team) in Women leading Science Event (7th of March 2025), in Oslo University

In 2023 and 2025, in the scope of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, UÉvora published testimonials from its female scientists¹⁰, in the first year with texts published on the UÉvora website and, this year, with a promotional video available in several communication channels, including UÉvora social networks (Figure 4.1.3).

Figure 4.1.3: UÉvora “Women in Science” promotional video

UÉvora Sol2H2O technical-administrative team recommended to all the project team members:

- the "Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication" from the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) and suggested to take the quizzes on inclusive language available on the EIGE website¹¹;
- the NAU website 3-hour training course on "Gender Equality in Labour and Employment", run by the Instituto do Emprego e Formação Profissional, I.P. (IEFP - Institute for Employment and Vocational Training) and the Comissão para a Igualdade no Trabalho e no Emprego (CITE - Commission for Equality in Labour and Employment), only available in Portuguese¹².

A leadership training also took place with the UÉvora team, including Sol2H2O's researchers, in May 2025 (Figure 4.1.4), as referred to in D3.3 (section 3.2).

¹⁰ <https://www.uevora.pt/ue-media/Mulheres-na-Ciencia>

¹¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/toolkits-guides/gender-sensitive-communication/common-challenges-when-using-gender-sensitive-language>

¹² <https://www.nau.edu.pt/en/course/igualdade-de-genero-no-trabalho-e-no-emprego/>

Figure 4.1.4: Sol2H2O team in the leadership training in Évora

4.2 GE Events attended

To improve their knowledge and bring more content to the Sol2H2O GE seminars, the technical-administrative members of the UÉvora team participate in events related to GE, online or organised by the University (Figure 4.2.1). Table 4.2.1 lists these events.

Figure 4.2.1: The conference "The verb To Be in the feminine" as the cover of the UÉvora magazine "À Segunda" (cover headline: "UÉvora discusses the role of women in society")

Table 4.2.1: GE-related events attended by UÉvora Sol2H2O team members

Date	Event	Location/Organisation
April 2023	2nd Iberian conferences "The verb To Be in the feminine - Inclusion, Equality, and Health at work"	UÉvora
September 2023	Themed visit to the Évora Museum: "Where are the women?"	UÉvora and Évora's Frei Manuel do Cenáculo National Museum
November 2023	Woman Impact Summit	Online, Heroikka
February 2024	Webinar "Leadership in feminine"	Online, AMONET, the Portuguese Association of Women Scientists
June 2024	Civil Security for Everyone - Sex and Gender in Research on Civil Security	Online, European Research Area Workshops on the Gender Dimension in Research
September 2024	Webinar "Equality between women and men"	Online, State Legal Competence Centre, CIG - Commission for Citizenship and

		Gender Equality
November 2024	Webinar “Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition”	Online, EIGE
February 2025	Gender dimension in your Horizon Europe proposal	Online, Europa Media Trainings Webinar
May 2025	2nd edition of the Gender, Diversity, Citizenship colloquium	UÉvora
May 2025	“Science, Gender Equality and Women Scientists: Building Inclusive Research Environments”	Online, Ibero-American Program for Education in Human Rights, Democracy and Equality of the OEI and EU-Solaris ERIC

5. Sol2H2O GE SEMINARS

Task 1.4 includes the organisation of four dedicated seminars, alongside the Project Meetings (ProM) and hosted, in turns, by the Widening and the TOP partners, in M7 (CIEMAT), M13 (UNIPA), M19 (ITC), and M36 (UÉvora), which was accomplished, with a few adjustments to coincide with the project meetings.

Three seminars have already been held, and a fourth seminar will be organised along with the Project Final Meeting (#7). UÉvora technical-administrative Sol2H2O team organised and presented the seminars, with the collaboration of the UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion manager, and the participation of all partners teams.

The first seminar was held in M8, in Almería (see 5.1 ProM#2 GE Seminar), the second seminar in M14, in Palermo (see 5.2 ProM#3 GE Seminar), and the third seminar in M21, in Pozo Izquierdo (see 5.3 ProM#4 GE Seminar), and the fourth seminar will be organised, as foreseen, in M36, in Évora (see 5.4 ProM#7 GE Seminar).

After the presentations, the seminars included guided discussions regarding the actions to be taken in Sol2H2O and GE perceptions. In some of the seminars, there was greater interest among women in actively participating in the discussion.

One of the main conclusions of the debates was that parenting, especially for new parents, particularly mothers, is where there are greater difficulties in balancing personal/family life and professional life and more negative consequences for the careers of female researchers.

5.1 ProM#2 GE Seminar

The first Sol2H2O GE seminar, presented by UÉvora, in July 2023 (M8), in Almería. A summary of this seminar is presented in Table 5.1.1, and it focused on why to include gender dimension topics in the project, some concepts related to the theme were clarified (the glass ceiling effect, the cement ceiling effect, and the Matilda effect), a comparison between UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA GE Plans and applied or suggested measures in these plans (see section 3), main achievements - mandatory GEPs, more often discussions on the GE topics, legislation, more women in leadership positions, more flexible parental leave policies, more inclusive working environments - and main problems in GE - how to report gender-based discrimination or violence, there are still less women in STEM, lack of consequences to the offenders - the publication of the “Code of conduct for the prevention and combat of harassment at work in UÉvora” in June 2023, how to do a GE assessment in Sol2H2O, with the presentation of T1.4 in the project proposal, and examples of measures to be taken (Appendix 2).

Table 5.1.1: ProM#2 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#2 GE Seminar
Date	4 July 2023
Project Month	M8
Location/Host	Plataforma Solar Almería / CIEMAT
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s Sol2H2O technical-administrative support)
Participants	UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA Sol2H2O teams participating in ProM#2
Number of participants per gender	9 men, 6 women
Duration	60 minutes
Main topic	Consortium GEPs comparison, GE concepts, GE achievements and problems, Sol2H2O GE actions

For the discussion, along with the presentation, the participants were asked for their opinions on the presented topics and asked to talk about specific situations where they experienced or witnessed situations of gender discrimination.

From the proposed general GE measures, the participants debated on the more suitable ones to apply to the project, and the conclusion was to carry on organising the dedicated seminars, to apply anonymous questionnaires to the consortium teams, and a smaller version of it to FTS participants (see section 6), to analyse the gender balance in the project teams and institutions (see section 2), but also in the participants of Sol2H2O FTs, by asking them to identify their gender when registering.

Figure 5.1.1: ProM#2 GE Seminar presentation slide

5.2 ProM#3 GE Seminar

Table 5.2.1 summarises the ProM#3 GE Seminar. The seminar started with a presentation focusing on the *Rush hour of life*, unconscious bias related to gender, for instance, unconscious bias in the job market. Some recent Portuguese news and statistics regarding the gender pay gap were presented, a comparison of the percentage of employees by gender in UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA, a comparison of the parental leave in Portugal, Spain and Italy, as well as a review of the GE assessment in Sol2H2O, Deliverables, and the percentage of T1.4 completion, 35% (Appendix 2).

Table 5.2.1: ProM#3 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#3 GE Seminar
Date	9 January 2024
Project Month	M14
Location/Host	Palermo / UNIPA
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s Sol2H2O technical-administrative support)
Participants	UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA Sol2H2O teams participating in ProM#3
Number of participants per gender	8 men, 7 women
Duration	90 minutes
Main topic	<i>Rush hour of life</i> Unconscious bias HR information on gender in the Sol2H2O partners' institutions and parental leaves comparison in the partners' countries Sol2H2O GE survey pilot test

Regarding the parental leaves in the three countries represented in the Sol2H2O consortium (Figure 5.2.1), highlighting the fact that Spain is one of the few countries where parental paid leave is equal for fathers and mothers, breaking down discrimination in hiring. A pilot version of the Sol2H2O GE survey was presented and tested in this seminar (see section 6).

PALERMO, 09.12.01.2024

Parental leaves

Figure 5.2.1: ProM#3 GE Seminar presentation slide, and ProM#3 GE Seminar participants

5.3 ProM#4 GE Seminar

Table 5.3.1 summarises the ProM#4 GE Seminar. The UÉvora presentation started focusing on some of the most significant results of the Sol2H2O team's survey preliminary results, with 17 answers by then, and the FTS survey, with 31 answers by then. The European Commission campaign #EndGenderStereotypes¹³ was also presented, as well as the percentage of T1.4 completion, 45% (Appendix 2). A brief presentation of the UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion was held. ITC presented “Working for gender equality at ITC”: some results from the quantitative diagnosis made in ITC, showing that, in general, the number of women and men is balanced, but 56% of the staff didn’t answer the inquiry, and of the staff who answered, 31% are men, 18% do not identify with one of the genders and 51% are women. In general, it is more important for women, and they are more aware of gender inequalities than men. In ITC, there are 12 top positions, and only 2

¹³ https://end-gender-stereotypes.campaign.europa.eu/index_en

are occupied by women. UNIPA presented the GE aspects and their GE Plan, emphasising the EIGE¹⁴ statement that “GE increases jobs and productivity”.

Table 5.3.1: ProM#4 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#3 GE Seminar
Date	24 September 2024
Project Month	M21
Location/Host	Pozo Ezquierdo, Gran Canaria / ITC
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s Sol2H2O technical-administrative support) Célia Peralta (UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion) Morena Rizzo (UNIPA) Hector Martinez and Antonio Ortegón (ITC)
Participants	UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA Sol2H2O teams participating in ProM#4
Number of participants per gender	10 men, 10 women
Duration	150 minutes
Main topic	Sol2H2O GE surveys preliminary results campaign #EndGenderStereotypes Working for gender equality at ITC Brainstorming Measures to propose to the partners’ administrations

A brainstorming session followed, focusing on: micromachism, gender-sensitive language, co-responsibility, conciliation, gender violence, diversity, gender identity in companies and organizations, and hidden and early signs of gender-based violence. To finish, the participants were asked for suggestions on Measures to propose to the partners’ administrations (see section 9), highlighting that more training on GE is needed for all staff, but especially for the GE working groups, as they are not all experts in the subject, nor have their working time totally devoted to it.

Gender Equality aspects (T1.4) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sol2H2O GE survey results - Seminar: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Working for gender equality at ITC” - Brainstorm addressing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Micromachism • The importance of language • Co- responsibility • Conciliation • Gender violence • Diversity • Gender Identity in companies and organizations • Hidden and early signs of gender-based violence - Measures to propose to the partners’ administrations regarding GE 	UÉvora (D. Livreiro / C. Peralta) UNIPA (M. Rizzo) ITC (A. Ortegón/ H. Martínez)
--	--

Figure 5.3.1: ProM#4 GE Seminar agenda

¹⁴ European Institute for Gender Equality - <https://eige.europa.eu/>

5.4 ProM#7 GE Seminar

The next GE seminar will be held along with the project’s final meeting, scheduled for the 11th and 12th of November 2025, in Évora, hosted by UÉvora. Table 5.4.1 summarises the foreseen contents for a presentation and a visit.

Table 5.4.1: ProM#7 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#7 GE Seminar
Date	11 or 12 November 2025
Project Month	M36
Location/Host	University of Évora, Évora / UÉvora
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s Sol2H2O technical-administrative support) Collaboration: Célia Peralta (UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion) and ASM Association
Participants	UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA Sol2H2O teams participating in ProM#7
Number of participants per gender	
Duration	30 minutes + visit
Main topic	Sol2H2O survey final results Presentation of T1.4 results Visit to an exhibition on the subject of equality

In view of preparing this last GE seminar, the UÉvora Sol2H2O team, in collaboration with the Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion, is going to propose a partnership with a local non-profit association, Associação Ser Mulher¹⁵, to visit an exhibition on the subject of equality.

After a presentation regarding Task 1.4 results, including the surveys and their conclusions, the ProM#7 participants will be invited to a guided visit to the exhibition.

6. SURVEYS

The objective of the GE surveys was to understand the perceptions of this topic among project team members and FTSS participants, to receive their opinions and suggestions on what to address in the seminars, and to understand the relevance they consider addressing GE to have, in general and in the context of scientific research.

To this end, a questionnaire was used in the two twinning projects at the UÉvora, Sol2H2O and SALTOpower¹⁶, based on examples of surveys used by partners in these consortia. In order to improve their knowledge of how to develop the questionnaire, the UÉvora technical-administrative team attended an open lecture held at the university.

After developing the questionnaire, it was tested in a paper pilot version at the next ProM (Sol2H2O ProM#3). Participants who tested the pilot version suggested that the questions should be answered on a scale of agreement, rather than with “yes and no” answers, as they felt that in some cases the answers would not apply so strictly.

A second version was developed and put into Google Forms format to facilitate its application, both with Sol2H2O teams and with FTSS participants, for whom a version

¹⁵ <https://sol2h2o.caosermulher.wordpress.com/about/>

¹⁶ Project SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03, GA Number: 101079303

without the last three questions was made, as these are questions that concern to working in the project (Appendices 3 and 4).

The questionnaire was then applied, using QR Codes, respectively, in ProMs #3, #4, #5, and #6 (keeping the first version, with “yes and no” answers, so as not to lose the answers given by participants in ProM#3 who might not have another opportunity to answer all questions), and in FTS#1, #2 and #3, so that team members and FTS participants who hadn’t answered before had the chance to do it, advising them to respond only if they had not already done so on a previous occasion. The questionnaires were also sent by email, with the link, in an attempt to increase the number of responses, in order to improve the representativeness of the samples.

It should be noted that the questionnaires are **anonymous**, to allow for unconstrained replies, and took about 5 minutes to fill out. Almost 60% of the FTSs participants filled in the questionnaire (46 answers from non-repeated participants), and 82.76% of the team members (24 answers, taking into account the 29 team members reported in M34, see Table 2.2.2.1).

6.1 Sol2H2O teams GE Survey

The survey was presented in ProM#3 (after which 17 answers were received), #4 (21 answers), #5 (21 answers, all participants had answered previously), and #6 (24 answers) and sent by email, using a QR code and the link to the Google Forms with the questionnaire.

According to Table 2.2.2.1, the proportion of women in the four partners total is 51.72%, and 48.28% of men, which is similar to the gender of the members who answered the questionnaire: 58.30% women and 41.70% men, but showing a little more interest from women.

24 team members from the four partners (including young and senior researchers, and other staff) responded to this survey as presented in Appendix 3. This sample size corresponds to a confidence level of 75% and a margin of error of 8.45%¹⁷, meaning that, statistically, this sample is not significant, nevertheless, it allowed for the gathering of useful information.

Some of the answers are analysed in Table 6.1.1.

Table 6.1.1: Teams GE Survey analysis

Question	Answers	Analysis
4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?		5 persons answered “Don’t know/won’t answer” (26.4%), although all partners institutions have GEPs. From the people who know the GEP exists, only 50% have read it (question 4.1). More dissemination or training is necessary.

¹⁷ <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>

<p>6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?</p>	<p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>Although most people have not experienced this discrimination, eight people reported that they had, and of these, 75% are women. Though 75% referred to it as being in a previous or outside work/study places. It should be noted that two people (one woman and one man) mentioned that it was <u>in their current place of study/work</u> (question 6.1).</p>
<p>8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organisation?</p>	<p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>Most part of the answers (58.3%) don't agree or "Don't know/won't answer", but only 45.8% (question 8.1) know specific measures, referring only to (question 8.1.1): "Homeoffice" "Flexibility" "Right to disconnect" "Kindergarten" "Sport facility".</p>
<p>10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?</p>	<p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>70% of the people did not feel this discrimination, but 3 people did (2 women and a man).</p>
<p>11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?</p>	<p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>17 people said they don't often hear or say sexist comments, 6 people answered "yes" (50% women and 50% men), and 1 person answered "don't know/won't answer", which may indicate a lack of awareness about what can be considered sexist comments. 100% of the people who answered "yes" said that they "hear" rather than "say" sexist comments.</p>
<p>12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?</p>	<p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>14 people answered "yes" (57.14% men), from which 3 referred that it was <u>in the current work/study places</u> (2 men and 1 woman, question 12.1). From the 9 people who described the situations</p>

		<p>(question 12.1.1), it is worth noting the two responses that refer to the current place of work/study:</p> <p>“Depending on the lead person, he listens and/or considers suggestions and requests of some men and not equally when they come from women” (answered by a woman)</p> <p>“- Lower rate of female PhD students progressing to research positions - sexist comments - parental rights/obligations leaning towards women” (answered by a man).</p>								
13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>33.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>66.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Don't know/ won't answer</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Yes	33.3%	No	66.7%	Don't know/ won't answer	0%	<p>Most people answered “no”, but 8 people (50% men and 50% women) answered “yes”, 3, all women, referring that it was “<u>at their current place of work/study</u>” (questions 13.1 and 13.1.1):</p> <p>“From male teachers to female students” “Relationships between professors and students” “A man harassing some young women”.</p>
Response	Percentage									
Yes	33.3%									
No	66.7%									
Don't know/ won't answer	0%									
14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organisation?	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Don't know/ won't answer</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Yes	83.3%	No	16.7%	Don't know/ won't answer	0%	<p>The majority (83.3%) of the people know how to report a complaint in these situations, but there are still people who don't know.</p>
Response	Percentage									
Yes	83.3%									
No	16.7%									
Don't know/ won't answer	0%									
15. In your opinion, is it important to address gender equality issues in research projects such as Sol2H2O?	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>87.5%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>8.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Don't know/ won't answer</td> <td>8.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Yes	87.5%	No	8.3%	Don't know/ won't answer	8.3%	<p>87.5% agree that it is important to address GE in research projects, and 79.2% agree that there is gender equality in the Sol2H2O project (question 16).</p>
Response	Percentage									
Yes	87.5%									
No	8.3%									
Don't know/ won't answer	8.3%									

6.2 FTSS GE Survey

The survey was presented in FTS#1 (after which 31 answers were received), FTS#2 (42 answers), and FTS#3 (46 answers in total) and sent by email, using a QR code and the link to the Google Forms with the questionnaire.

The proportion of women in the FTSS, in total, is 40.5%, and 59.5% of men, which is slightly different from the gender of the persons who answered the questionnaire: 45.7% women and 54.3% men.

46 FTS non-repeated participants from the three editions (including young and senior researchers, and other staff) responded to this survey as presented in Appendix 4. This

sample size corresponds to a confidence level of 71% and a margin of error of 9.23%. Statistically, this sample is not significant, but it allowed for a brief analysis, Table 6.2.1.

Table 6.2.1: FTSS GE Survey analysis

Question	Answers	Analysis
4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	32.6% of participants answered “Don’t know/won’t answer”, and from the 65.2% participants who know the GEP exists, only 42.2% have read it (question 4.1). More dissemination or training is necessary.
6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	14 participants, from whom 85.71% are women, have experienced gender discrimination. 5 people referred (question 6.1) that it is in their current work/study organisation. 6.5% of the participants answered “Don’t know/won’t answer”, which may demonstrate a lack of awareness of what is considered gender discrimination.
<p>1. 7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organisation?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p> ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 </p>	89.1% of participants think that there are equal opportunities, but also 43.5% agree that there are inequalities in top positions (question 7.1).
<p>2. 8.1. Do you know any work-life balance measures available in your organization?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	Though 52.2% of participants agree that there is a work-life balance in their work/study organization (question 8), only 28.3% know which measures are available. 71.7% answered “no” or “Don’t know/won’t answer”, which indicates that more dissemination or training is necessary, if these measures exist.

<p>9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (orange), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>23.9% of the participants agree that women and men are assigned different tasks, of whom 72.73% are women.</p>
<p>10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (orange), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>4 participants felt this discrimination, all women.</p>
<p>11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (orange)</p>	<p>26.1% of participants often hear (question 11.1) sexist comments.</p>
<p>12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (orange)</p>	<p>19 people answered “yes” (68.42% are women), including 2 people in the current work/study place (question 12.1). 4 people answered “don’t know/won’t answer”, which may indicate a lack of awareness about what can be considered gender discrimination. 6 participants described the situations, and 2 women answered (question 12.1.1 - Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names?): “I do not want to do this” “I’d rather not”. Even though this was an anonymous survey, these responses may indicate that there is still difficulty in discussing this topic across different generations (one of the women is between 18 and 30 years old, and the other is over 60).</p>

<p>13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p>	<p>16 people (62.5% women) answered “yes”, 6 referring that it was “at their current place of work/study”, identifying four situations (questions 13.1 and 13.1.1):</p> <p>“Harassment of young women and students on occasions”</p> <p>“Improper behavior of professors towards female students”</p> <p>“A teacher that snapped a colleague’s butt in front of lots of others students”</p> <p>“One colleague that followed me to the toilets every time, it was long ago”.</p>
<p>14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organisation?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p>	<p>Just over half (52.2%) of the participants know how to report a complaint in these situations.</p>

7. GE IN THE Sol2H2O COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The GE theme has also been addressed in the project's communication channels (see D5.2), as detailed below, celebrating International Women's Day, publishing about the seminars, highlighting PhD completions, and introducing the team members. Until the end of the project, other releases will be made, for instance, the #EndGenderStereotypes campaign will be announced in the newsletter and can also be shared on social media, and the survey results will be available on the website.

7.1 Meet our team

The *Meet our team* heading allowed introducing the Sol2H2O partners' teams, while also giving visibility to women, both scientists and other employees working in the project. It was published both on the project's social networks (Instagram and LinkedIn) and newsletters. This heading included a picture of the team member and four short-answer questions, one of which regarding GE: “According to your experience and the Gender Equality seminars promoted at Sol2H2O, what can be improved in this area?”. The answers received are presented in Table 7.1.1.

Table 7.1.1: “Meet our team” GE question and answers

<p>According to your experience and the Gender Equality seminars promoted at Sol2H2O, what can be improved in</p>	<p>“The promotion of this discussion, alone, is already an important step to put GE questions on the Agenda, also to show that these questions affect both genders.”</p>
	<p>“My feelings are that on numerous occasions, it is treated from the perspective of motherhood, when a marked gender stereotype not associated with it continues to exist. So, approaching it from other perspectives is also necessary.”</p>
	<p>“Statistics show that there is still a lack of gender equality in Portugal and Europe, for example, concerning salaries earned, so it is important to continue to address this issue in all contexts, as it is a culturally-rooted issue. In the case of research, top positions are more difficult for women to fill, and in the seminars we've already organized with the project teams, we've discussed ideas</p>

this area?	on how to improve.”
	“I believe that gathering information from all institutions has been crucial for identifying improvements for each partner, based on the comprehensive data collected.”
	“I think the project promoted well the Gender Equality”
	“I think they are very well organized and that the entire Sol2H2O team is aware of this issue. But it is very important to continue emphasizing them to truly achieve equality.”
	“yes they are”
	“I believe that the Sol2H2O Gender Equality Seminars are an essential contribution to demystifying some of the preconceptions that many people make. In general, I think it's important for research teams to have these moments to talk about emerging issues such as Gender Equality, because it's these small contributions that have the possibility of helping to change the current paradigm, taking into account the location and specific tasks of each area.”
	“It seems to me that equal access to High management positions and an appropriate work-life balance would definitely improve Gender Equality.”
	“I promote gender equality in all the activities that I coordinate from the Water Department. Historically, the water sector has been a male-dominated area and gender equality actions are encouraging equal participation.”
“Equal opportunities to access senior management positions, together with a better balance of work and family life, for both women and men, which does not force women to bear the majority of the burden of managing a household, these are things that would help improve the current situation.”	

Eleven team members responded to this short interview, as presented in Figures 7.1.1, 7.4.1 and 7.4.2.

Figure 7.1.1: Meet our team publications on Sol2H2O Instagram

7.2 Website

In the Sol2H2O website (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/>), the WP leaders and the team members are presented (Figure 7.2.1), news referring to the GE seminars (mentions to seminars along ProM, Figure 7.2.2), and to the leadership training (see section 4.1) are published (Figure 7.2.3).

Figure 7.2.1: Sol2H2O WP leaders and team members on the website

During this Seminar, the attendants were invited to participate in the debate, focusing on why it is important to have gender equality, some concepts related to this theme, like the glass ceiling effect, the cement ceiling effect and the Matilda effect, the main achievements in this area and the main problems still to solve. A comparison between the four partner institutions Gender Equality Plans was made and a strategy to do a continuous Gender Equality assessment in Sol2H2O was defined. Along the next project meetings, this theme will be further discussed.

Figure 7.2.2: News about the online GE seminar on the Sol2H2O website

Figure 7.2.3: News about the Leadership training on the Sol2H2O website

Survey results, including the ones regarding GE (see section 6), will be published on the website, always ensuring anonymity and complying with data protection rules.

7.3 Newsletters

The Sol2H2O newsletters¹⁸ included the *Meet our teams* headings (newsletter #6), PhD completions (Figure 7.3.1; newsletter #11), news about GE seminars along with project meetings (Figure 7.3.2; newsletter #1).

PhD Thesis – Isabel Requena

Isabel Requena successfully defended her PhD thesis on the development and evaluation of solar-powered membrane distillation (MD) systems operated in batch recirculation mode for brine concentration. The objective of the research was to determine the viability of this technology as a sustainable solution for managing saline waste streams.

Her work demonstrated that solar-driven MD systems hold strong potential for efficient and environmentally friendly brine concentration. The thesis was awarded the qualification of Excellent.

Figure 7.3.1: PhD Thesis completion in Sol2H2O newsletter

¹⁸ <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#newsletters>

Gender Equality Seminar #1

The Sol2H2O **first Gender Equality Seminar** took place in Almería, along the #2 Project Meeting, on the 4th July 2023, with **attendants from all the consortium partners** (UEVORA, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA).

During this Seminar, the attendants were invited to participate in the **debate**, focusing on why it is important to have gender equality, some concepts related to this theme, like the **glass ceiling effect**, the **cement ceiling effect** and the **Matilda effect**, the main achievements in this area and the **main problems still to solve**. A comparison between the four partner institutions Gender Equality Plans was made and a **strategy to do a continuous Gender Equality assessment** in Sol2H2O was defined. Along the next project meetings, this theme will be further discussed.

Figure 7.3.2: News about the online GE seminar in the Sol2H2O newsletter

7.4 Social networks

In Sol2H2O social networks, Instagram¹⁹ and LinkedIn²⁰, GE-related publications were made regarding *Meet our team* (Figures 7.4.1 and 7.4.2), the leadership trainings (Figure 7.4.3), mobilities, and International Women's Day (Figure 7.4.4).

Figure 7.4.1: *Meet our team* publication on Sol2H2O Instagram

¹⁹ <https://www.instagram.com/sol2h2o/>

²⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/sol2h2o>

Figure 7.4.2: Meet our team publication on Sol2H2O LinkedIn

Figure 7.4.4: International Women's Day post in Sol2H2O Instagram

7.5 Project video

The project video was published on Sol2H2O YouTube²¹ and website, and it presents Sol2H2O, with interviews with all WP leaders, one per partner (Figure 7.5.1), which means that there are no interviews with women in the video, although female researchers from the team do appear (Figure 7.5.2).

Figure 7.5.1: Project video interviews with WP leaders

²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tGojclZHW3c&list=PLtmABrST4ziqc2g2GP9M8Tjuis1MablgV&index=11>

Figure 7.5.2: Sol2H2O researcher in the project video

8. GENDER EQUALITY ACTION BARRIERS

The main barriers to implementing the Gender Equality task in Sol2H2O were to define concrete actions to take, and a general lack of interest in the subject, because although it is commonly agreed that there should be equal rights and duties between men and women, measures are not always well accepted, and events almost always focus on the same general topics, leading to a devaluation of the subject.

Albeit having an excellent relationship with the University of Évora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion, it only has one employee, who divides her work between GE and other types of inclusion, both for workers and university students.

Another difficulty is obtaining statistical representativeness in the surveys conducted, as the teams and participants in the FTSs are relatively small populations, in addition to the aforementioned lack of interest.

The difficulties in collecting data and participating in debates may also be related to the sensitivity of the topic, even though the anonymity of the surveys was guaranteed, which is impossible to achieve in seminar discussions.

The project timeframe is limited for profound structural changes, given the 36-month timeframe, but the Task 1.4 (WP1) proposed objective was achieved: *to monitor and enhance Gender Equality measures and aspects*, as detailed in the Conclusions, and actions to recommend were learned, both to propose to partner institutions (see section 9), and for upcoming projects, it would be important to include GE actions more frequently in scientific projects, in addition to declaring the existence of an institutional GEP. There should be systematic inclusion of gender indicators in scientific and management reports. Another good practice is the integration of gender-themed seminars into regular technical project meetings, promoting horizontal participation.

One suggestion for monitoring gender proportion at events is to ask for gender information when participants register, using forms to ensure data confidentiality (as Sol2H2O did in the FTSs, but not in the symposiums), since gender is something with which each person identifies and cannot be inferred by observing people/names on attendance lists.

9. MEASURES TO PROPOSE TO THE INSTITUTIONAL ADMINISTRATIONS

As a result of Gender Equality's assessment actions in the Sol2H2O project, a list of measures to propose to the administrations of UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA is presented, in view of further improving the inclusion of all in these institutions. Some of the measures mentioned are already being implemented by some of the consortium partners' institutions, but are a proposal to the other institutions, and in some cases, it has been found that they are not known to all employees, like all the work-life balance measures already implemented.

1. To include gender data for all employees in the Human Resources database, so that at any moment, a gender balance of the institution can be assessed;
2. Awareness campaigns and training regarding Gender Equality and gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, are needed, so that people can better identify and report these situations, without being afraid of retaliation;
3. Reporting channels or who to approach in situations of gender-based violence or sexual harassment are not well-known to all employees, more dissemination of this information is necessary;
4. Since the use of inclusive language is essential for equal communication, institutions must have guides, in the local language and in English, which should be disseminated or training provided to employees, so that institutional and scientific documents are not discriminatory, as well as the institutional communication;
5. Work-life balance measures already proposed should be effectively implemented and disseminated among the employees;
6. Childcare services, summer camps available for longer periods, covering more age groups and with more places and day care centres for elderly cohabiting parents, provided by the institutions or in partnership with them, at affordable prices, would facilitate employees' work-life balance;
7. Increasing women's visibility as researchers, technicians, etc., with promotional videos and school visits;
8. In the case of educational institutions, include gender equality issues in more study programmes;
9. Strengthen Gender Equality offices so that they can carry out more activities and implement/disseminate measures more easily;
10. Promote the inclusion of Gender Equality measures and discussions in more scientific projects;
11. To offer part-time positions so that people can have a better work-life balance and flexible schedules;
12. To make packages that include families when a researcher goes into mobility available;
13. Welcoming people who arrive at institutions, using measures such as the "Living Amenities Facility" that Sol2H2O has implemented;
14. The interruption, whether due to parenthood, illness, or any other reason, must not affect the researchers' (and other staff) careers, so their assessment system, for example, should take this into account;
15. Safety clothes are almost always purchased in "men's sizes", which are not suitable for all sizes of men and women, and may even make them less secure. Purchases more suitable for all workers should be taken into account;
16. With regard to occupational diseases and accidents at work, as well as gender-related health issues, institutions should take gender into account, promoting health for women employees, doing gender-related workplace risk assessments, and considering sex-specific differences in health outcomes, disease prevalence, and treatment responses.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The SheFigures 2024 report²² shows that there is still some way to go in the European Union towards Gender Equality. In the case of countries represented in the Sol2H2O consortium, this report highlights that there have been many improvements, and there is still a need for:

- in Spain, further improvements are needed to increase top positions held by women, as well as supporting women to nurture their efforts as innovators;
- in Italy, further actions are needed to increase outputs for women researchers, particularly as authors of publications and patent inventors;
- in Portugal, further efforts are needed to increase the proportion of women among researchers in the business enterprise sector and to increase women's opportunities for career advancement and participation in decision-making.

In that report, a “She Figures Index” was developed as a tool to measure the extent to which EU member states have achieved GE in the European Research Area, and the results for the countries represented in the Sol2H2O consortium are presented in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: *She Figures Index* in Portugal, Italy and Spain

The surveys applied in Sol2H2O allowed access to some GE perceptions, and evidence that more awareness is needed. The debates in themselves were important, getting to know the teams better, creating an environment where everyone can express themselves, and empowering women in the team.

The conclusions for each of the five recommended action topics are detailed below.

10.1 Work-Life Balance and Organisational Culture

Sol2H2O implemented initiatives promoting well-being and quality of life ('Living Amenities Facility'), which aimed to improve work-life balance, particularly relevant for female researchers.

More information about the conciliation measures that exist in the institutions is needed, as the surveys showed that only 45.8% (project teams) and 28.3% (FTS participants) know some measures, and the ones they referred to know were quite limited compared to those that are referred to in GEPs. This may also indicate, in addition to a lack of awareness, that these measures, although considered in theory, are not actually being implemented.

²² European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>

The Sol2H2O GE seminars and the debates in themselves were productive, and talking about the topic is one of the goals achieved, as mentioned in one of the Meet the Team interviews, “The promotion of this discussion, alone, is already an important step (...)”. The debates and the GEP comparison lead to the proposals that can be presented to the UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA administrations (see section 9).

10.2 Gender Balance in Leadership and Decision-making

The gender balance analysis showed that in UÉvora, there were more women working than men, but in top positions, the proportion is the opposite. In CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA, there are fewer women employees than men, in general, and it is worse in top positions.

In Sol2H2O teams, overall, there was an improvement in the gender balance, although there are more male researchers and more women in “other staff”, and the top positions (WP leaders) are all occupied by men.

The leadership trainings held in UÉvora and in ITC were a good practice action that can be replicated in other projects.

10.3 Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression

In recruitment, priority should be given to the underrepresented gender in the department that is recruiting, in cases where there is equal classification in the selection criteria.

One of the main conclusions of the seminar discussions was the difficulty of career progression, which is generally accentuated in the case of women, due to parenthood or caring for other people (descendants, ascendants, etc.). Measures should be taken to compensate for these absences, as well as absences due to illness, such as an adjustment in the classification systems for researchers.

In Portugal, FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, the Portuguese Ministry of Education and Science department that evaluates and funds scientific research activities, created the RESTART²³ program, promoting gender equality and opportunities through the competitive funding of individual R&D projects, in all scientific fields, when carried out by researchers who have recently taken parental leave, including adoption.

10.4 Integration of the Gender Dimension into Research and Teaching Content

It is definitely important to include the gender dimension in research, and the Sol2H2O survey showed that 87.5% of the respondents agreed that it was important to address GE in Sol2H2O.

UÉvora, as a teaching institution, already includes this topic in some of its study programmes, and the GEP indicates that it intends to extend it to more courses, which is extremely important in the current context of increasing gender-based violence among young people.

10.5 Measures against Gender-based Violence, including Sexual harassment

Gender-based harassment at work is a problem within the area of research and innovation in higher education environments²⁴, and the Sol2H2O surveys refer several times to student harassment by teachers.

²³ <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/outros-apoios/programa-restart/>

²⁴ European Commission: Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, *2025 report on gender equality in the EU*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2838/5262357>

Furthermore, in the FTS GE survey, almost half of the respondents said they did not know what to do or who to reach to report gender-based violence. There is a need to publicise the reporting channels available in the institutions. It was also mentioned in the seminar discussions that in many cases reports are not made, either because of fear of negative consequences for the victims or because of the perception that the perpetrators face very few consequences, namely if they are in top positions.

The Sol2H2O FTS GE survey also showed that gender based discrimination and harassment are more often felt or witnessed by women (68.42% and 62.5%).

10.6 Other relevant topics

Although women generally show more interest in the GE topic, as was perceived in some of the seminars, with almost only women participating in the GE events attended by the technical-administrative team, and it was also a result of the UÉvora perception report, in the Sol2H2O surveys, this was not significantly verified. The gender proportions of respondents are not very different to the proportion of participants' gender, indicating slightly more interest from women, albeit reduced, in general, given the low number of responses.

Sol2H2O suggests strengthening institutional equality policies, integrating gender into more projects, and continuing to hold seminars and training sessions on Gender Equality.

11. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The *Data Management Plan* describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in a project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive in Google Drive. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A and B) <Grant Agreement-101079305-Sol2H2O-1.pdf>	Project folder
3	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
4	Deliverables acceptance note <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.26-05-2023.v1.0.xls>	Project Folder
5	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
6	Data Management Plan <SOL2H2O_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_15-05-2023_v_2>	Project Folder
7	GE seminar in ProM#2 <SOL2H2O_WP1_Gender Equality_Almería_july23>	Project Folder
8	GE seminar in ProM#3 <Sol2H2O_PoM#3_Day1_and_WP1_and_GE>	Project Folder
9	GE seminar in ProM#4 <Sol2H2O_ProM#4_Day1> <2024 09 24 Working for gender equality at ITC> <SOL2H2O_UNIPA-RIZZO-22-9-24>	Project Folder

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
10	Gender Equality Plans folder <Gender Equality Plans>	Project Folder
11	Gender Inclusive communication guides folder <Gender Inclusive communication guides>	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: GE SEMINARS PRESENTATIONS

- ProM#2 GE Seminar

European Twinning for research in Solar energy to (2) water (H2O) production and treatment technologies
GA Number: 101079305
European Research Executive Agency REA.C3

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA

Gender Equality

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04-06.07.2023

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04-06.07.2023

2

Structure

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04-06.07.2023

3

Structure

Introduction

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023

4

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04.-06.07.2023

Why?

“The achievement of effective equality between women and men is an elementary factor in achieving a more developed and just society.”

Plan de Igualdad 2021-2025, ITC

Gender difference as a positive working tool for teams: different approaches, different points of view contribute to research.

Introduction

5

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04.-06.07.2023

Your opinion...

Do you think there is gender equality:

- in general?
- in your institutions?
- in Sol2H2O?

Introduction

6

Concepts

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023

7

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04.-06.07.2023

49,6% women in world population
38,7% women in the workforce
(2020)

Concepts

Dra. M^a Dolores Arenas e Dra. Berta Puértolas, Universidad de Extremadura in "A mulher no trabalho: desigualdade e barreiras de género", II Jornada Ibérica "O verbo Ser no feminino".

8

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA 04.-06.07.2023

The glass ceiling effect

The glass ceiling (invisible barrier) effect is the pervasive resistance to the efforts of women and minorities to reach the top ranks of management in organizations.

Causes:

- socio-cultural factors
- gender roles and stereotypes
- corporate management culture in companies
- sociocultural preconceptions that make it difficult for men to take orders from women
- etc.

9

Concepts

Cement ceiling effect

Cement ceiling is an expression that refers to the internal barriers unconsciously self-imposed by women themselves at the time of career advancement to higher positions of responsibility.

Causes:

- family responsibilities
- domestic work
- career break due to pregnancy and breastfeeding
- etc.

Concepts

The Matilda effect

The Matilda effect is a bias against acknowledging the achievements of women scientists whose work is attributed to their male colleagues. This phenomenon was first described by suffragist and abolitionist Matilda Joslyn Gage.

Concepts

Matilda

Rosalind Franklin

F. Crick and J. Watson
DNA

Now recognized as an important contributor to the 1953 discovery of DNA structure.

Sol2H2O

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Gender Equality Plans

In common

European and national legislation, Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans.

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

In common

- Situation diagnosis (enquiries, HR information);
- Objectives to be achieved (planning) and tools (implementation);
- Monitoring.

Differences

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;

Use of non-sexist language, drafting of a practical guide

Teleworking

Online awareness campaigns

Childcare services and summer schools

Psychological consultation

Flexibility of schedules, shifts

Satisfaction questionnaire

Gender Equality
Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

16

Differences

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;

Breastfeeding room (since 2018)

Social action plan for costs with dependents

Adequacy of work space for pregnant women

Right to disconnect

Meetings with a maximum of 2 hours

Time management workshops

Takeaway meals service

Longer parental leave

Gender Equality
Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

17

Differences

2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;

Monitoring the composition of the leadership bodies

Training with experts and mentoring

Gender Equality
Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

18

Differences

3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;

Equality in selection boards (1 woman if 3 members or 2 women if 4 members)

Positive discrimination in hiring

Celebration of international Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th february)

Highlighting women in Science days

Gender Equality Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

19

Differences

4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;

Training and raising awareness

Include this theme in the study programmes, master's and doctoral degrees in this area

Awards and economic incentives for female students in STEM

Gender Equality Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

20

Differences

5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

enquiries	quick guidebook	video	webpage
scientific and artistic events	Training	lack of knowledge of the law	

Complaints

How, to whom, how to manage, conduct codes

Gender Equality Plans

UÉVORA, CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA

21

Conclusions

- Predominantly non-sexist cultures, but certain positions or functions occupied by men;
- Women more interested in this theme;
- The need to use inclusive language;
- Questions about how or to whom to report.

Gender Equality
Plans

22

Sol2H2O

UNIVERSIDADE
DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Main achievements

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023
23

- Gender equality plans;
- More often discussion of the topic;
- Legislation;
- More women in leadership positions;
- More flexible parental leave policies;
- More inclusive working environments.

Main
achievements

24

Assinado por: HERMINIA MARIA DE VASCONCELOS ALVES VILAR
Número de identificação: 06000714
Data: 2023/06/26 18:52:34+01:00
Certificado por: Diário da República Eletrónica.
Atributos certificados: Notário - Universidade de Évora

DESPACHO N.º 79/2023

Código de conduta para a prevenção e combate ao assédio no trabalho na Universidade de Évora e Serviços de Ação Social

Ao abrigo do disposto na alínea n) do n.º 1 do artigo 23.º dos Estatutos da Universidade de Évora, homologados pelo Despacho Normativo n.º 7/2021, publicado no Diário da República, 2.ª série, n.º 30, de 12 de fevereiro 2021, após consulta pública, é aprovado e posto em vigor o "Código de conduta para a prevenção e combate ao assédio no trabalho na universidade de Évora", que se anexa ao presente despacho e que deste passa a fazer parte integrante.

A Reitora da Universidade de Évora, em 26 de junho de 2023

Main achievements

Code of conduct for the prevention and combat of harassment at work at the University of Évora

Sol2H2O

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Main problems

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023

- How to report?
- Men should be part of the discussion?
- Women are against themselves?
- Less women in STEM?
- Specific examples?

Main problems

Of the total number of scientists and engineers, only 40% are women.
Hostile and sexist working environments, the assignment of boring tasks, the pay gap and the lack of career development and recognition.

<https://epale.ec.europa.eu/pt/blog/desigualdade-de-genero-na-educacao-stem>

Provedor do Estudante

É o encarregado de assegurar que os alunos têm as condições necessárias para o sucesso dos seus estudos...

Provedor do Trabalhador Não Docente e Não Investigador

É o encarregado de assegurar que os trabalhadores não docentes e não investigadores têm as condições necessárias para o sucesso do seu trabalho...

Canal de Denúncia Interno

Hierarchical superior
Rector

Are the consequences for offenders fair?

Main problems

Sol2H20

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023

29

Task 1.4: Gender Equality (Leader: UEVORA; Participants: CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA) M1-M36

Led by UEvora-SCC, this task aims at the development and implementation of questionnaires, monitoring procedures and enhancement strategies aiming Gender equality in the access to research and technical-administrative positions in the Consortium institutions.

Grounded on the individual experience of the female participants in the project, Gender equality measures will be discussed and presented in 4 dedicated Seminars alongside Project Meetings and hosted, in turns, by Widening and TOP partners. The description and assessment of Gender Equality measures will be presented in a dedicated D1.6.

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
 2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
 3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
 4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
 5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.
- a. Enquires - **compare, merge and distributed**
 - b. HR information; - **compare statistics**
 - c. Dedicated seminars; - **next meetings**
 - d. Enhancement strategies; - **table with differences in the 4 plans**
 - e. Monitoring procedures, e.g. (indicators);
 - f. Positive discrimination of women in hiring;
 - g. Salary review to guarantee equality;
 - h. Apply these measures also to FTS? - **monitoring**

Sol2H20

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Deliverables

TABERNAS, ALMERÍA, 04.-06.07.2023 33

Deliverable No and Name	TYPE	DUE DATE
D1.6 Gender Equality Report	R — Document, report	M34

WP1 Deliverable

- ProM#3 GE Seminar

Sol2H20

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA
Dominique Livreiro

Gender Equality aspects

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

Structure

Rush hour of life

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

The *rush hour of life**

*Torres, A., et al. (2019). Work, family and living conditions in Portugal and Europe

30 to 49 years old

A period of intense pressure resulting from competing or even contradictory demands:

- it's the time to form a family, but also
- the time for professional affirmation and progression.

This phase tends to be experienced differently: women spend, on average, more time looking after their families.

Rush hour of life

↓
more pressure, more physical and psychological fatigue

↓
higher consumption of antidepressants

Unconscious bias

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

Unconscious bias

Unconscious biases are learnt assumptions, beliefs or attitudes of which we are not necessarily aware. Everyone has such biases (are formed at 3/4 years of age) and resorts to them as mental shortcuts for faster information processing.

- Skin colour
- Level of education
- Age
- Socio economic status
- Accent
- Weight
- Sexuality
- Gender

Unconscious bias

Unconscious gender bias are unintentional and automatic mental associations, originating from traditions, values and experience, that establishes natural different roles for women and man.

- Unconscious gender bias remains a significant barrier to women's career advancement. It is difficult to identify and prevent.
- Unconscious gender bias remains a significant barrier to men's participation in household tasks, caring for children and the elderly.

Unconscious bias in the job market

- Typically female jobs include babysitters, preschool and kindergarten teachers, nurses, and receptionists.

- Typically male jobs include truck drivers, electricians, and firefighters.

Portuguesas ganham menos 13% do que os portugueses, diz estudo da CGTP

Agência Lusa - AG
9 mar, 09:24

Diferença é maior entre os que ganham mais dinheiro

ORDATA
ESTATÍSTICAS EUROPEIAS PORTUGAL E EUROPA

ESTATÍSTICAS PUBLICAÇÕES QUADROS RESUMO SIMULADORES CENSOS 2021 CINCO DÉCADAS DE DEMOCRACIA

Paridade + Portugal + Emprego e Mercado de Trabalho + Salários

Disparidade entre sexos no ganho médio mensal dos trabalhadores por conta de outrem: total e por nível de qualificação

Qual é a diferença no salário médio, por mês, com horas extras, subsídios ou prémios, entre mulheres e homens em percentagem do salário médio mensal dos homens?

Indicador
Total (taxas de qualificação)

2021	-16,0 %
1985	-27,1 %

Comparar aqui para ver a gráfico animado

P SOCIEDADE EDUCAÇÃO SAÚDE JUSTIÇA MEDIA FLORESTAS PÚBLICO NA ESCOLA MAIS ▾

EXCLUSIVO NATALIDADE

Desigualdade salarial entre homens e mulheres ajuda a afundar a natalidade em Portugal

O facto de as mulheres ganharem menos do que os homens é um dos entraves à natalidade, diz estudo. A precariedade dos jovens também ajuda a explicar porque têm os portugueses cada vez menos filhos.

Natalia Faria
2 de Junho de 2023, 15:00

Assine já

“The increased presence of women in the labour market has not resulted in a decrease in fertility, but the wage gap between women and men has. Women invest more time in their professional qualifications. However, they still earn less and are less represented in top positions. And this pay gap results in fewer financial resources for women to plan their parenting decisions (...).”

Sol2H2O

Dominique livreiro

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H2O

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
 2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
 3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
 4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
 5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.
- a. Enquiries - **compare, merge and distributed**
 - b. HR information; - **compare statistics**
 - c. Dedicated seminars; - **next meetings**
 - d. Enhancement strategies; - **table with differences in the 4 plans**
 - e. Apply enquiries also to FTS - **monitoring**

HR information

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

* only considering teachers and researchers (excluding technical administrative staff)

Parental leaves

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

Portugal: leave of 28 working days for the father, paid at 100% of salary, and up to 150 days for the mother.

Spain: both parents can have 16 weeks of paid leave (100% of salary).

Italy: 10 working days leave for the father, and 5 months for the mother, but paid at 80% of salary (with a maximum limit).

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE
assessment in
Sol2H2O

Work-life balance and organisational culture				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Use of non-sexist language and drafting of a practical guide	x	x	x	x
Teleworking	x	x	x	x
Awareness campaigns and training activities	x	x	x Online	x
Childcare services	x	x	x	x
Summer schools				x
Flexibility of schedules	x	x	x	x
Shifts		x		
Right to disconnect	x		x	

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE
assessment in
Sol2H2O

Work-life balance and organisational culture				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Meetings with a maximum of 2 hours	x			
Time management workshops	x			
Takeaway meals service	x			
Longer parental leave/Sabbatical semester	x			x
Satisfaction questionnaire		x		
Breastfeeding room (since 2018)		x		
Social action plan for coets with dependents		x		
Adequacy of work space for pregnant women			x	
Correct the score in the performance evaluation in case of maternity leave	x			
Psychological consultation				x

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE
assessment in
Sol2H2O

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Monitoring the composition of the leadership bodies	x	x	x	x
Training with experts and mentoring	x	x	x	x

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

Gender equality in recruitment and career progression				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Equality in selection boards	x	x	x	x
Positive discrimination in hiring (preference to persons of the under-represented gender)			x	
Celebration of international Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th february)	x	x		
Highlighting women in Science days		x		
Award for outstanding research in the field of gender studies	x			
A minimum of 1/3 of people of each gender in teams applying for project funding	x			

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Training and raising awareness	x	x	x	x
Include this theme in all the study programmes	x			x Master's or doctoral degrees
Awards and economic incentives for female students in STEAM				x

Gender Equality Plans - a comparison

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H20

Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment				
Measure	UÉvora	CIEMAT	ITC	UNIPA
Training	x Scientific and artistic events	x	x	x Quick guidebook; Videos; Webpage
Complaints: how, to whom, how to manage, conduct codes	x	x	x	x
Regular questionnaires				x

Enquiries

Continuous GE assessment in Sol2H2O

Gender Equality assessment in Sol2H2O

START

This enquiry is anonymous and the data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Florin) and will be stored in a folder restricted to Sol2H2O partners (EVORA, ITC, CERMAT and UNIPA) until the end of the project (2025).

Answer the following questions by selecting only one of the available answers and only elaborate on your answers when lines are provided. This questionnaire takes about 5 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance.

1. Sector
 - University
 - Public research and technology organization
 - Industry
 - Private research and technology organization
 - Other
2. Gender
 - Female
 - Male
 - Non-binary
 - Other
 - Prefer not to say
3. Age
 - 18-30
 - 31-40
 - 41-50
 - 51-60
 - > 60
4. Does the institutions where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Don't know/ won't answer

Sol2H2O

Deliverable

PALERMO, 09.-12.01.2024

52

Deliverable No and Name	TYPE	DUE DATE
D1.6 Gender Equality Report	R — Document, report	M34

WP1 Deliverable

WP1 completion

Cooperation Management

Task	Done	To do
T1.4 Gender Equality	Seminars HR information	Seminars Enquiries HR information D1.6

- ProM#4 GE Seminar

Sol2H20

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

DLivreiro, CPeralta, MRizzo, AOrtegón, HMartínez

Gender Equality aspects

POZO IZQUIERDO, 24.-27.09.2024

Sol2H20 GE survey results

17 answers

2. Gender
17 respostas

Gender Equality

Sol2H2O GE survey results

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?
17 respuestas

Gender Equality

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

100%

Sol2H2O GE survey results

10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?
17 respuestas

Gender Equality

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

100%

Sol2H2O GE survey results

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?
17 respuestas

Gender Equality

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

54,5%

45,5%

Sol2H2O GE survey results

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?
17 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

13.1. If yes, ...
6 respuestas

Sol2H2O GE survey results

15. In your opinion, is it important to address gender equality issues in research projects such as Sol2H2O?
17 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

16. In your opinion, is there gender equality in the Sol2H2O project?
17 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

31 answers

2. Gender
31 respuestas

● Female
● Male
● Other
● Prefer not to say

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

5. In your opinion, is there gender equality... 5.1. in society in general? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "...I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
31 respuestas

5.2. in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
31 respuestas

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?
31 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

100%

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?
31 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

87,5%

12,5%

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?
31 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

75% 25%

Gender Equality survey results - FTS

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?
31 respuestas

● Yes
● No
● Don't know/ won't answer

72,7% 27,3%

#EndGenderStereotypes

#EndGenderStereotypes

#EndGenderStereotypes

<p>44%</p> <p>of Europeans think that the most important role of a woman is to take care of her home and family.</p>	<p>36%</p> <p>is how much less women overall earn on average compared to men.</p>
<p>82%</p> <p>of persons working part-time for care reasons are women.</p>	<p>69%</p> <p>of Europeans think women are more likely than men to make decisions based on their emotions.</p>

Seminar

Gender Equality

PRESENTATION
"Working for gender equality at ITC"

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Micromachism

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

In order to tackle gender inequality, we must look at the way we communicate. Using gender-sensitive language can:

- Make it easier to see important differences between the needs of women and men;
- Challenge unconscious assumptions people have about gender roles in society;
- Lay the foundation for greater gender equality throughout society;
- Raise awareness of how language affects our behaviour;
- Make people more comfortable with expressing themselves and behaving in ways that were once not considered 'typical' of their gender.

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Co-responsibility

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Conciliation

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Gender violence

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Diversity

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Gender identity in companies and organizations

Brainstorm

Gender Equality

Hidden and early signs of gender-based violence

Measures to propose to the partners' administrations regarding GE

Gender Equality

Dedicated resources to GE departments
Compulsory training and dedicated courses to all, but specially to the GE departments
More financing
Lesson 0 on GE
Part-time jobs/flexibility available for researchers or other staff who have children or elderly
Measures to compensate leaves or other situations (eg pandemics), when women produce less scientific contents
To be able to take the family on business trips

T1.4 completion

Gender Equality

Task	Done	To do
T1.4 Gender Equality	Seminars HR information Surveys	Seminars Surveys HR information D1.6

APPENDIX 3: SOL2H2O TEAM GE SURVEY

Perguntas Respostas 24 Definições

Secção 1 de 2

Gender Equality assessment in Sol2H2O

B *I* U

This inquiry is **anonymous** and the data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored in a folder restricted to Sol2H2O partners (UEVORA, ITC, CIEMAT and UNIPA) until the end of the project (2025).

Please, answer the following questions by selecting only one of the available answers and only elaborate on your answers when lines are provided.

This questionnaire takes about 5 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance.

1. Sector
24 respostas

- University
- Public research and technology organization
- Industry
- Private research and technology organization
- Other

2. Gender
24 respostas

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

3. Age

24 respostas

4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?

24 respostas

4.1. If yes, have you read it?

20 respostas

5. In your opinion, is there gender equality... 5.1. in society in general?

24 respostas

5.2. in your work/study organization?

24 respostas

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?

24 respostas

6.1. If yes, was it ...

8 respostas

7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organization?

24 respostas

7.1. In upper management positions, are there gender inequalities?

24 respostas

8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organization?

24 respostas

8.1. Do you know any work-life balance measures available in your organization? Which one?

24 respostas

8.1.1. If yes, kindly specify:

10 respostas

- Flexibility - a few hours for conciliation.
- Telework.
- Flexibility in working time.
- Kindergarten, sport facility
- Flexibility in telework.

- We can have some very minor flexibility if children are <12.
- Schedule flexibility, flexible working hours.
- Home office
- The right to disconnect.
- Flexibility

9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category?

24 respostas

10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?

24 respostas

11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?

24 respostas

11.1. If yes, ...

6 respostas

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?

24 respostas

12.1. If yes, ...

14 respostas

12.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

9 respostas

They (the company) didn't let my husband go on paternity leave because they had to hire another person in his position.

- Lower rate of female PhD students progressing to research positions
- sexist comments
- parental rights/obligations leaning towards women

Depending on the lead person, he listen and/or considers suggestions and request of some men and not equally when they come from women.

In private companies, it happened to see a boss (male) misbehaving with an employee (female).

In the street, men say inappropriate things to women, for example.

Continuously in society (roles, even jobs).

I saw different tasks assigned to women in the same job category.

- I don't want to be a mother and people tell me that sure in a near future (2-3 years), I will want.
- People think that I have to know for example what there are in the fridge because I am a woman.

Clients asked to talk to a male technician to solve their malfunctions.

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?

24 respostas

13.1.If yes, ...

8 respostas

13.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

5 respostas

Sexist comments of sexual nature by male to female colleague.

A man harassing some young women.

Very often in society, especially nightlife.

In previous place of work a man was spying and photographing a female colleague.

Relationships between professors and students.

From male teachers to female students.

14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organization?

24 respostas

15. In your opinion, is it important to address gender equality issues in research projects such as Sol2H2O?

24 respostas

16. In your opinion, is there gender equality in the Sol2H2O project?

24 respostas

17. Do you have suggestions on how to improve gender equality in the Sol2H2O project (e.g. providing part-time job vacancies, providing personal protective equipment in sizes suitable for women and men)?

8 respostas

Part time job vacancies.

Open discussions within an open forum/in seminars would be interesting. Something like brainstorming in gender issue.

Promote (when possible) participation of meetings to a balanced number of males and females.

There is not much that can be done since it reflects the fact that we are mostly men in our topics. Positive discrimination might be used.

Make possible the mobilities with the family.

The availability to travel for a meeting project or Fast track school can be a problem. To reduce the number of them can help.

More women in steering committee.

Existe igualdade neste projecto, quer pela parte prática como parte teórica.

APPENDIX 4: FTSS GE SURVEY

Perguntas Respostas 46 Definições

Secção 1 de 2

Gender Equality assessment in Sol2H2O

B *I* U ↻ ✕

Mais

This enquiry is **anonymous** and the data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored in a folder restricted to Sol2H2O partners (UEVORA, ITC, CIEMAT and UNIPA) until the end of the project (2025).

Please, answer the following questions by selecting only one of the available answers and only elaborate on your answers when lines are provided. In questions with options 1 to 5: 1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree".

This questionnaire takes about 5 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance.

1. Sector

46 respostas

2. Gender

46 respostas

3. Age

46 respostas

4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?

46 respostas

4.1. If yes, have you read it?

45 respostas

5. In your opinion, is there gender equality... 5.1. in society in general? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

46 respostas

5.2. in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

46 respostas

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?

46 respostas

6.1. If yes, was it ...

16 respostas

7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organization? (1 mean...artially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

46 respostas

7.1. In upper management positions, are there gender inequalities? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
46 respostas

8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
46 respostas

8.1. Do you know any work-life balance measures available in your organization? Which one?
46 respostas

8.1.1. If yes, kindly specify:

13 respostas

- Home office possible
- A little flexibility for parents with children younger than 12
- Flexible schedule, reduced work hours, etc
- Schedule flexibility
- Flexible working hours
- I know that parents have time flexibility when they need to pick up kids from school or stay with them at home. I also know that there was an experimental project that gave 15min of daily laboral gymnastic in all University.
- Reduce of work schedulle in summer

- Working time flexibility
- flexible hours
- Flexibility in the initial and final time of work.
- The official schedule is until 16:30 and for people who are father/mother can start one hour later and finish one hour later. Also, there are permissions for the care of children.
- Right to disconnect
- Labor time reduction in summer and winter

9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially"...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

46 respostas

10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents? (1 mean...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
46 respostas

11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?
46 respostas

11.1. If yes, ...
12 respostas

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?

46 respostas

12.1. If yes, ...

19 respostas

12.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

8 respostas

Constantly in society

I'd rather not

Little and almost not visible things that contribute for the big picture, like putting women group receiving participants on an event just because of their gender. Or taking in count suggestions made by women that won't have the same weight as men's suggestions.

I do not want to do this

Sexist comments from teachers, different treatment from either teachers and colleagues

Not considering suggestions coming from women against men from lead person in the institution.

I decide not become a mother and some people have told me: sure, in a couple of years, you change your opinion. Also, a man told me that I have to know what there is in my fridge because I am the woman of the house.

In a technical support, clients often asked to talk with a male technician.

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?

46 respostas

13.1.If yes, ...

16 respostas

13.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

9 respostas

Improper behavior of professors towards female students

Sometimes during nightlife out

Night life

I'd rather not

A teacher that snapped a colleague's butt in front of lots of others students.

No

One girl during a party by more guys

One colleague that followed me to the toilets every time, it was long ago

Harassment to young women and students in occasions.

14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organization?

46 respostas

15. Do you have suggestions?

 Copiar gráfico

3 respostas

